

Navigating the Path to Efficient and Just Transition to Carbon Neutrality: A Case Study of Agricultural Practices in Foya District, Liberia

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Abstract:

The importance of shifting towards carbon-neutral agriculture is increasingly recognized globally, particularly in developing countries. This study focuses on Foya District in Liberia, examining the relationship between traditional farming methods and emerging sustainable practices, and evaluating the carbon footprint of local agricultural activities. To address this, a novel framework called the Adaptation Strategies Index and Problem Confrontation Index (ASI-PCI) has been proposed to evaluate the hurdles local farmers face in adapting to climate change, along with their adaptive behaviors and strategies. The ASI of 564 highlights the use of drought-resistant

crops, while the PCI of 566 indicates significant challenges due to extreme climate events. Key sources of greenhouse gas emissions identified include deforestation, land use changes, and rice cultivation. Quantitative data reveals that 63% of farmers engage in rice cultivation, 39.3% in deforestation, and 27.7% in land use changes, contributing to carbon emissions. The Multiple Linear Regression (MLR) analysis showed that education level positively influences farmers' strategies for carbon-neutral agriculture ($P < .001$), validating the initial hypothesis. The study explores strategies to reduce emissions, such as introducing drought-resistant crops, implementing irrigation systems, adopting mixed cropping practices, and promoting agroforestry. The study emphasized the pivotal role of women in participating in local farming initiatives, highlighting the group's potential for better carbon-neutral agriculture practices. It underscores community engagement's importance in identifying barriers to adopting carbon-neutral practices. The insights gained aim to guide rural communities in the region and beyond, providing a framework for policymakers, stakeholders, and practitioners to develop pathways toward carbon neutrality that support local economic stability and development.

Keywords: *Agriculture, carbon neutrality, greenhouse gases, traditional farming, just transition.*

Introduction

Climate change impacts food security on a local, regional, and global scale (Filho, 2020). Food distribution may be affected by an increase in the strength and frequency of extreme weather patterns, which would raise prices globally (Brown, 2015). Considerable adaptation

measures will be necessary to preserve current commodities, expand output, and ensure that food quality matches demand (World Bank 2021). Agriculture is the main source of livelihood for more than 60% of Africans (Denkyirah, Okoffo, Adu, & Bosompem, 2017). This sector must be

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sustainable to ensure sufficient food production, while also protecting the environment and alleviating poverty(Ogemah, 2017). Although agriculture fulfills society's essential need for food production, it must be carried out in a manner that does not jeopardize global food security or ecological services(Bennetzen, Smith, & Porter, 2016; Otim, Watundu, Mutenyo, Bagire, & Adaramola, 2023), and the industry can positively impact the environment by significantly reducing carbon emissions through investments in tree planting and afforestation(Pata, 2021; Rehman, Fareed, Salem, Kanwal, & Pata, 2021) and every region of the world should make this a priority to have a safe environment.

Africa possesses 60% of the global untapped arable land, although only 6% of its total land area is dedicated to agricultural activities(John I, 2023). The primary concern confronting the continent is the attainment of self-sufficiency in food production and distribution(Idris A. Ayinde¹, 2020). Liberia is one of the few countries in West Africa that is thought to be particularly sensitive to the effects of climate change, and its agriculture sector contributes to more environmental degradation as compared with other African countries(IPCCC, 2019). The transition to carbon neutrality in agriculture for Africa has been researched in numerous research articles. According to Balogh W, et. al, Sub-Saharan Africa has suffered badly and will continue to bear the consequences of climate change due to its limited adaptation and reaction to global warming paired with an increased level of poverty(Balogh & Kurino, 2020). Due to its geographical position in Africa, Liberia is susceptible to severe climatic conditions, the coastal ramifications of rising sea levels, and fluctuations in water systems and water accessibility(USAID, 2017) and it is anticipated to worsen severe weather events and reduce crop production, leading to food insecurity(USAID, 2012), which is bad for the country because most of its farmers practice subsistence farming that primarily depends on rainfed.

A critical gap exists in current research on sustainable agriculture in Africa. While many studies explore the challenges, few directly

address practical adaptation strategies for local farmers. This lack of focus on implementable solutions hinders progress towards building resilience to carbon-neutral agriculture. This research identified a gap by investigating the adaptation practices employed by farmers in Liberia's Foya District to transition to carbon neutrality.

This research utilized the ASI and PCI framework to investigate adaptive practices and strategies adopted by local farmers in the Foya District as they transition to carbon-neutral agriculture. Multiple linear regression (MLR) was employed to analyze the impact of four independent variables on the dependent variable, ASI. The results aim to provide policymakers and stakeholders with valuable grassroots insights to prioritize adaptation initiatives. Understanding key factors influencing farmers' attitudes and adaptive actions can also improve adaptation strategy implementation in similar regions of Liberia and neighboring countries.

Materials and Methods

To get a better picture and understanding, the study evaluated farmers' resilience strategies such as the ability to adapt and recover from the adverse effects of extreme weather and their planned farm behaviors to adjust to this unpredictable weather. As seen in Figure 1, a descriptive survey design was used to generate data through questionnaire interviews of the respondents and from published articles. The rainfall and temperature data were collected from authorities at the Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) and the Ministry of Agriculture (MOA). The (ASI) was used to evaluate and prioritize the efficacy of various strategies in response to change, specifically about climate change and environmental obstacles. Also, a similar approach was used to calculate the (PCI) to measure and prioritize the challenges encountered by farmers. Additionally, the rainfall and temperature of the study area were analyzed to examine the temperature and precipitation patterns in the study area.

Figure 1. Framework of the Research Process

The most effective method to communicate farmers' understanding of long-term changes in climatic variables and their causes is using descriptive statistics such as frequencies, percentages, and averages. (Kaur Parampreet, Stoltzfus Jill, & Vikas, 2018). SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Science) software was used to analyze data on adaptation methods. Respondents rated various strategies on a 4-point scale (1=no importance, 4=high importance) to assess their relative significance. These ratings were coded in the ASI (potentially referring to an Adaptation Strategy Index) formula, where 1=no importance and 4=high importance. Equation (1) then calculated the relative importance of each adaptation strategy.

$$ASI = ASn \times 0 + ASI \times 1 + ASm \times 2 + ASh \times 3 \quad (1)$$

Where:

ASI = Adaptation Strategies Index

ASn = Frequency of respondents ranking the adaptation method as having no importance

ASl = Frequency of respondents ranking the adaptation method as having low importance

ASm = Frequency of respondents ranking the adaptation method as having moderate importance

Ash = Frequency of respondents ranking the adaptation method as having high importance

The study also employed a ranking system (PCI - possibly Problem Confrontation Index) to identify barriers to adaptation. Farmers rated each barrier on a 4-point scale (1=no barrier, 4=high barrier). Similar to the adaptation strategies, these ratings were coded in the PCI formula Equation (2) where 1=no barrier and 4=high barrier.

$$PCI = Pn \times 0 + Pl \times 1 + Pm \times 2 + Ph \times 3 \quad (2)$$

Where:

PCI = Problem Confrontation Index

Pn = Number of farmers who rank the barriers as no problem

Pl = Number of farmers who rank the barriers as a low problem

Pm = Number of farmers who rank the barriers as a moderate problem

Ph = Number of farmers who rank the barriers as a high problem

The MLR was used to identify the factors influencing farmers' adaptation to climate change. Accordingly, these factors include personal attributes (gender, age, education, agricultural experience). (Ru Guo, Yunyang Li, Li Shang, Cuiyang Feng, & Wang, 2021). Farmers' adaptation to climate change varies depending on their local ecological, social, and economic factors. Previous research has used various ways to investigate the relationship between several elements influencing an individual's perception and adaptive behavior (Below Till B et al., 2012; Ntanos, Kyriakopoulos, Chalikias, Arabatzis, & Skordoulis, 2018; Towfiqul, Shill Badhon Kumar, Salam Roquia, Siddik Md Nur Alam, & Ahmed, 2021). These methods can be broadly separated into three categories: logistic regression, multiple regression, and linear regression. To explore the intricate interaction between several elements that can potentially affect farmers' perceptions of and adaptive behavior toward climate change, multiple linear regression (MLR) is used in this study. Some suggested basic questions were asked:

Q: What variables influence local farmers' adaptation to climate change?

The input variables of MLR refer to various elements that may impact local farmers' adaptation to climate change, whereas the outcome variables are the yes/no answers to the question. Equation (3) was used to analyze the MLR.

$$Y = b_0 + m_1x_1 + m_2x_2 + \dots + m_px_p + e \quad (3)$$

Where:

y = Dependent variable (or Response variable)

x_p = Independent variables (or Predictors)

m_p = Slope Coefficients for each independent variable or predictor

b₀ = Constant term (or y-intercept)

e = Residual or model error term but usually neglectable in practical term

Foya, as shown in Figure 2, is the second-largest districts in Lofa County with a population of 73,312 inhabitants (LISGIS, 2008), and has three clans, constituting nine towns. and operates as Lofa's agricultural hub. Figure 2 (a) is the geographical map, while (b) is the land use, land cover map. The landscape of Foya covers 16,145 hectares of mechanized agriculture that produces sugar cane and rice, and another 537 hectares of semi-mechanized agriculture that produces rice and palm oil (IDH, 2021), and its forest (164,628 ha (406,800 acres) are the three proposed national reserves. It has the Foya Afforestation Project, which is a National Plantation area covering 9,062.4 ha (22,394 acres) (USAID, 2017).

The study targeted nine towns in Foya District (Ndendu Town, Mendigisua-II Town, Kpandu Town, Kenema Town, Bambodu Town, Sodu Town, Koniadu Town, Ngesu-Lor Town and Fassema Town). The communities were picked following a week of field observation by volunteers. The study employed purposive non-probability sampling to gather diverse perspectives on climate change's impact on local agriculture. Twenty-three community leaders (including town chiefs, youth leaders, and women leaders) were interviewed across nine towns. An additional 177 residents were surveyed in these towns, bringing the total sample size to 200. As seen in **Table 1**, participants were chosen based on the association to guarantee a fair and equitable viewpoint on the study.

Figure 2. The Study Area

Table 1. Targeted Respondent and Farmers' Association

Towns	Number of respondents	Farmers' Association
Ndendu	23	Foya Rural Women Cooperate
Mendigisua	23	Foya Rural Women Cooperate
Kpandu	23	Foya Rural Women Cooperate
Kenema	23	Foya Rural Women Cooperate & Foya Kamala Farmer Association
Bambodu	23	Foya Kamala Farmer Association
Sodu	23	Foya Kamala Farmer Association
Koniadu	21	Foya Kamala Farmer Association & Lofa Group of Farmers
Ngesu-Lor	21	Lofa Group of Farmers
Fasema	21	Lofa Group of Farmers
Total	200	

Source: Field Survey 2023

Results

Table 2 indicates that 64% of the participants were aged between 31 and 45. Individuals aged

31 to 45 are considered to be at the peak of their productive and economically active years, capable of making decisions that benefit them the most. During this era, farmers can assess the effectiveness of various measures for adapting to climate change to reduce negative impacts. Additionally, the table indicates that 19.5% of the participants were within the age range of 21 to 30 years. Only 16.5% of the responders were above 45 years of age.

The finding in Table 2 also revealed that over half (60%) of the respondents were female, and (40%) were male. The results confirmed the Ministry of Agriculture of Liberia's 2008 rural survey on agricultural households. According to the ministry poll, women in rural Liberia generate most of the food and are mostly responsible for the food security of their households. In addition, the results are consistent with the (MOGD and World Bank, 2010) research, which showed that households with female dominance have a higher substantial share of food crop growers than households with male dominance.

Table 2. Age and Gender Distributions of Respondents

	Age group (years)	Frequency	Percentages
Age	21 - 30	39	19.5
	31 - 40	72	36
	41 - 45	56	28
	46 - 50	33	16.5
	Total	200	100
	Gender	Frequency	Percentages
Gender	Male	80	40
	Female	120	60
	Total	150	100

Source: Field Survey 2023

The data in Figure 3 (a) indicate that 23% of farmers had reached a higher level of education, 27% secondary level of education, followed by 32.5% with primary education, and only 17.5% with no formal education. Formal education

would dramatically alter farmers' awareness of climate change and the best management strategies they apply to prevent its negative impact. From the data, it can be said that most of the farmers have formal or secondary education in the study area, which would positively influence their adaptation techniques to climate change. The level of farming expertise has a crucial role in determining how well farmers can adjust to climate change and the extent to which agricultural productivity is affected.(Amaza, Abdoulaye, Kwaghe, & Tegbaru, 2009).

The data in Figure 3 (b) revealed that half of the respondents, 56.5%, had farming experience between five to ten years. Additionally, 31.5% had eleven to fifteen years of experience, and 12% had farming experience between sixteen to twenty years.

Figure 3. (a) Respondents' Educational Level and (b) Farming Experience

The data in Figure 4 indicates that 60% of local farmers in the Foya district cultivate their crops in swampland and 30% cultivate their crops in arable lands to adapt to the adverse effects of climate change. While only 10% of the local farmers cultivate their crops in hilly area.

One essential strategy for farmers to adapt to climate change is to discover and switch to different crop varieties. The effects of climate

change frequently increase the demand for various agricultural mixtures. Farmers must replace crops with different varieties that are resistant to the rapidly changing climate. Utilizing annual or perennial versatile crops minimizes the adverse effects of climate change on agricultural systems and ensures consistent agricultural cultivation(de Sousa et al., 2021).

Figure 4. Land Cultivation Types in the Foya District

Figure 5 Types of Cultivated Crops Categorized

Figure 5 displays the types of planted crops that respondents utilized to adjust to climate change. The data shows that 9.3% of local farmers in the study area identified cocoa, cassava, and vegetable farming, 12% identified rice, fruits, cassava, and vegetable farming, 10% identified fruits, rice, and vegetable farming, 12% identified palm, rice, cassava, and vegetable farming, 13.3% identified cocoa, rice, and palm farming, 6% identified livestock, rubber and cocoa farming, 20% identified rice, cocoa, palm, and vegetable farming and 17.3% identified rice, cassava and vegetables planting as crops in the region that can withstand the adverse effects of climate change. The swampland and arable land rice farming, cocoa farming, and vegetable farming are the three different varieties of

farming choices for 63.9% of local farmers combined for cultivation. Also, 41.9% of the district's local farmers combined said that rice, cassava, and fruit productions are the best-suited crops for their cultivation and 20% of them said that is better to plant trees and grow cash crops like (palm, rubber cocoa) to mitigate the impact of climate change.

Irregular rainfall distribution patterns have a greater impact on small-scale agriculture. The data presented in Figure 6 shows that 64.5% of farmers observe a notable decline in precipitation, whereas 23.5% of farmers in the district report an increase in precipitation. Furthermore, 7.5% of respondents expressed the belief that the shift in precipitation is consistent, while 4.5% remain unaware of the distinctions in meteorological conditions within the study area. Local farmers in the district have reported a decrease in rainfall, which has impacted their farming efforts. Farmers report that the continuous decrease in rainfall is increasing warmth, which ultimately leads to crop failure and reduced output.

Figure 6. Farmers' Perspective of the Long-Term Precipitation Fluctuations in the Foya District

Furthermore, Figure 7 shows the precipitation trends in the Foya district over the last 30 years, from (1992-2022). As displayed, the lowest precipitation of 111.09 occurred in 2009, while

the highest intensity of 593.32 took place in the year 2011 and had a bad influence on local farmers, as the overflow of rivers and erosion damaged most of the crops during these periods.

Figure 7. Yearly Average Precipitation of Foya District (1992-2022)

Figure 8. Farmers' Impression of the Long-Term Fluctuations in Temperature in the Foya District

Rising temperatures often harm crop productivity (Zhao et al., 2017). Figure 8 demonstrates that 83.5% of the survey respondents observed a troubling increase trend in temperature, while 4.5% perceived a drop in the amount of sunshine. Additionally, 7.5% of respondents believed the district's temperature was still steady, while 4.5% were uninformed of the district's climate. The farmers said that they

had noticed an increase in the amount of sunshine, which eventually, they claim, generates heat waves during their farming season.

Figure 9. Yearly Average Temperature of Foya District (1992-2022)

Furthermore, Figure 9 data shows the rise and fall in temperature in the research area with a minimum of 603.13 that occurred in 1999 and an exponential rise of 899.64 in 2003 which seriously affected the farming season of local farmers. According to the farmers, the increase in temperature during these periods created water scarcity, degraded the soil quality and they were confronted with drought, and the higher reproductive rates of pests and diseases, which was difficult to control. The average temperature has been rising noticeably over the past 30 years.

Table 3 shows that 168 out of 200 farmers ranked drought-tolerant crops as the greatest adaptation technique in the district accounting, with an ASI of 564 and a ranking of 1. One hundred forty-two participants ranked irrigation or water splashing as their second option for climate change adaptation, with an adaptation strategy index score of 523 and a position rating of two. Additionally, 72 respondents ranked mixed crop practices as the third most important adaptation method, with a slot rating of 3 and an ASI of 389. With an Adaptation Strategy Index of (319) and a preference score of 4, 63 out of 200 farmers considered agroforestry somewhat necessary. The dry season garden resulted in 25 responders, with an ASI of 220 and a position of fifth. Reduction in farm size with twenty-one

respondents resulted in an ASI value of 192 and a position rank of 6. Nine respondents regarded off-farm work as less significant, resulting in an adaptation strategy index of 125 and a slot rank

of 7. The ASI score of 94 ranked at 8, indicates that most farmers did not consider change date in planting as a critical adaptation alternative.

Table 3. Farmers' Ranking of the Various Adaption Factors in Foya District

Farmers strategies	Adaptation	High Important	Moderate Important	Low Important	No Important	ASI	Adaptation Ranking Preference
Drought Tolerant Varieties		168	29	2	1	564	1
Use Irrigation & Water can		142	42	13	3	523	2
Practice Mixed Cropping		72	78	31	19	403	3
Agroforestry		53	61	38	48	319	4
Garden Practices During Dry Season		25	39	67	69	220	5
Reduction in Farm Size		21	39	51	89	192	6
Off-Farm Job		13	32	53	102	156	7
Change Date in Planting		11	23	49	117	128	8

Source: Field Survey 2023

Farmers in the study area are adapting to climate change through various methods, as shown in Figure 10. Drought-resistant crops are the most common strategy, adopted by 25.6% of households. Irrigation and cane watering systems are used by 22% of farmers, followed by mixed cropping (19.5%). Interestingly, 11.6% of

farmers see afforestation as a valuable adaptation strategy. Other approaches include dry-season gardening (10.3%), adjusting planting dates (2.5%), reducing farm size (4.4%), and seeking non-agricultural employment (4.2%). These diverse strategies highlight the farmers' resilience in the face of challenging weather conditions.

Figure 10. Local Farmers Implementation Management Strategies

To analyze the hypothesis, as seen in Table 4 – 8, the MLR was employed at 95% Coefficient intervals which showed a good model fit: $F(5, (194) = 10.218, P < .001, R^2 = 0.208$ and

$R^2\text{Change} = 208$. The analysis shows that education level had a positive effect on farmers' adaptive behaviors and strategies in the study area. ($\beta = 0.22, t = 3.28, P < .001$). Hence, the

hypothesis was accepted. The analysis shows that years of farming experience had a positive effect on local farmers in the district. ($\beta = 0.103$, $t = 1.56$, $P < .001$), indicating that two is accepted. The result shows that cultivated land type had a positive effect on farming activities in the study area. ($\beta = 0.111$, $t = 1.36$, $P < .001$),

which confirmed that hypothesis three is accepted. Lastly, the results found that the categories of crops grown had a positive effect on the adaptive behaviors of local farmers. ($\beta = 0.305$, $t = 3.85$, $P < .001$) and therefore also confirmed that hypothesis four is accepted.

Table 4. Variables Entered/Removed^a

Model	Variables Entered	Variables Removed	Method
1	Categories of crops grown, Years of farming experience, Education Level, Gender, Cultivated land type ^b	.	Enter

Source: Field Survey 2023

Note: a) Dependent Variable: Adaptation Strategies Index; b) All requested variables entered

Table 5. Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.457 ^a	.208	.188	.442	.208	10.218	5	194	.000

Source: Field Survey 2023

Note: a) Predictor (Constant), Cultivated land type, Education Level, Years of farming experience, Gender, and Categories of crops grown.

Table 6. ANOVA

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	9.963	5	1.993	10.218	.000 ^b
	Residual	37.832	194	.195		
	Total	47.795	199			

Source: Field Survey 2023

Note: a) Dependent Variable: Adaptation Strategies Index; b) Predictor (Constant), Cultivated land type, Education Level, Years of farming experience, Gender, Categories of crops grown.

Table 7. Coefficient^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B		Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Lower Bound	Upper Bound	Tolerance	VIF
		1	(Constant)	2.102			.179		11.761	<.001
	Gender	-.343	.069	-.344	-4.967	<.001	-.480	-.207	.851	1.176
	Education Level	.108	.033	.222	3.285	.001	.173	.243	.892	1.121
	Years of farming experience	.073	.047	.103	1.555	.122	.166	.220	.924	1.082
	Cultivated land type	.081	.059	.111	1.366	.174	.197	.236	.620	1.614

Categories of crops grown	.065	.017	.305	3.852	.001	.032	.099	.652	1.534
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Source: Field Survey 2023

Note: a) Dependent Variables: Adaptation Strategies Index

Table 8. Collinearity Diagnostics

Model	Dimension	Eigenvalue	Condition Index	Variance Proportions					
				(Constant)	Gender	Education Level	Years of farming experience	Cultivated land type	Categories of crops grown
1	1	5.240	1.000	.00	.00	.01	.00	.00	.01
	2	.263	4.462	.00	.03	.18	.02	.06	.32
	3	.251	4.566	.01	.10	.58	.00	.00	.01
	4	.141	6.095	.00	.08	.11	.80	.00	.03
	5	.082	7.976	.00	.01	.00	.08	.80	.63
	6	.022	15.403	.98	.78	.11	.09	.13	.00

Source: Field Survey 2023

Note: a) Dependent Variable: Adaptation Strategies Index

The impediments to farmers' adaptation to climate change adaptation are represented in Figure 11. According to the figures, 60.08% of respondents view the unpredictability of the weather as a serious hindrance to implementing their adaptation strategies. Also, 16.14% of the respondents highlighted the high cost of agricultural supplies and lack of access to financial help as impediments to climate change

adaptation strategy execution. In addition, 13.21% of farmers reported a lack of agricultural subsidies and extension staff, while 6.89% cited a lack of water sources during the dry season, such as the distance of the river, as a significant obstacle to implementing climate change adaptation strategies. 3.68% of interviewees reported significant hurdles to adapting to climate change.

Figure 11. Obstacles to Farmers' Adaptation Strategies

Table 9. The Extent of the Constraints to Adaptation Strategies

Obstacles to Climate Change Adaptation Variables	High	Moderate	Low	No Problem	PCI	Rank Adaptation Obstacles
Unpredictable Weather	171	25	3	1	566	1
Inadequate access to agri. subsidies and agri. extension workers	132	31	21	16	479	2
High cost of agri. inputs & limited access to financing facilities	100	42	34	24	418	3
Lack of access to water sources	71	52	41	36	358	4
Inadequate labors	16	61	81	42	251	5
Poor access to agri. market	4	54	84	58	204	6
Soil Fertility	1	29	92	78	153	7

Source: Field Survey 2023

Table 9 Shows that 171 respondents identified the unpredictable nature of the weather as the most significant obstacle to their plan modification strategies, with a PCI value of 566 and a ranking of 1. The second most significant obstacle, with a PCI value of 479 and an order of 2, was a lack of agricultural subsidies and extension workers. Farmers in the district ranked lack of financial help and high agricultural supply costs as the third most critical problems in adapting to climate change (PCI score of 418). Water shortage during the dry season, including river distance, was highlighted with a PCI score of 358 and a ranking of 4. The PCI emphasizes the gravity of the various challenges or difficulties

As indicated in Figure 12, 39.29% of farmers in Foya district feel deforestation is the primary source of climate variation in their area. Additionally, 27.68% of respondents identified subsistence farming/shifting cultivation as a significant contributing factor. 18.81% blame God or ancestral spirits for the district's bad weather, while 14.22% are unaware of the daily fluctuations in temperature and rainfall. Data indicate a link between human activity and climate change, including deforestation and shifting farming. Farmers in the district identified two activities that significantly contribute to climate change at the global, regional, and national levels.

Figure 12. Carbon Footprint in the Study Area

Discussion

The carbon-neutral agricultural commodities approach (CNAC) identifies solutions for integrating agricultural sectors into a worldwide carbon-neutral future (FAO, 2022). Carbon-neutral agricultural practices encompass the utilization of climate-resilient crop varieties, minimizing the application of fertilizers and pesticides, enhancing carbon sequestration through soil organic carbon and agroforestry systems, adopting renewable energy sources, and optimizing energy efficiency across food supply chains (Johnson, 2021). Transitioning to carbon-neutral agriculture, farms/fields should be allowed to remain uncultivated for specific periods using leguminous cover crops to help enhance soil fertility, reduce emissions, and

promote nitrogen fixation in the soil. Farmers in Foya district must use an alternative method such as controlled burns or mulching to reduce emissions instead of traditional burning practices for land clearing. Another strategy is maximizing water efficiency and integrating organic matter into paddy fields and the release of methane linked to this farming technique can be minimized. In addition, by incorporating shade trees into cocoa plantations, carbon emissions can be minimized while simultaneously enhancing the quality and quantity of cocoa beans. To further strengthen the strategies for a carbon-neutral transition, there must be an established knowledge-sharing platform and collaboration on climate-smart agriculture (CSA) practices. Training programs that emphasize climate-smart practices, soil health management, and composting techniques provide farmers with the knowledge and skills they need to effectively implement these strategies, especially targeted women farmers who play crucial roles in agriculture to provide equitable participation in the transition.

The Government of Liberia should optimize and focus on rules to assist farmers in enhancing resilience, including regulations on water usage, seed registration efficiency, fertilizer testing, labeling, and registration, and market financing to facilitate the transition to carbon-neutral agriculture and promote sustainable and inclusive growth in the Foya district. Such as providing knowledge on (CSA) which will encourage the adoption of practices to cover cropping, improved fallows, and efficient irrigation to minimize emissions and enhance the sequestration of carbon in the soil. Also, incorporating the planting of trees (agroforestry) into agricultural practices will offer numerous benefits, such as providing shade, preventing wind erosion, and enhancing soil fertility through nitrogen fixation. These efforts collectively contribute to reducing carbon footprints and support sustainable development. There should be resource mobilization for local farmers and a clear land ownership right that will encourage long-term investments in sustainable practices by local farmers.

Conclusion

The study explored how local farmers are adapting to climate change and the challenges they face in adopting sustainable practices. 200 farmers were surveyed. Most were women between 31 to 45 with 5-15 years of experience. Swampland and arable cropping were seen as the most effective land management techniques. Root vegetables, rice, and vegetables were viewed as best suited for the changing climate. Farmers reported decreased rainfall and rising temperatures as key challenges.

The survey in the Foya district revealed farmers' adaptation strategies to climate change. Most grow drought-resistant crops like cassava and vegetables alongside rice. Irrigation (using the Mayo River and boreholes) is a common adaptation tactic. Education positively affects farmers' adaptation behaviors. Unpredictable weather is the biggest hurdle, followed by limited access to finances and agricultural inputs (including subsidies and extension workers). Farmers believe deforestation and shifting cultivation contribute most to climate change. Understanding these challenges is crucial for developing programs to support sustainable farming in Foya.

Therefore, this research would suggest that the government of Liberia and its partners should organize research groups that will effectively use the ASI-PCI framework to gather information from local farmers in other regions and neighboring countries on their perspectives on climate-related concerns, strategies for adapting to the changing climate, and challenges associated with transformation.

Based on the pivotal role of women in participating in local farming initiatives, there is need to elevate their potential for better carbon-neutral agricultural practices. The gender-responsive climate-smart agricultural practices can be tailored to address the unique needs and priorities of women farmers. These practices encompass methodologies like agroforestry, conservation agriculture, and water-efficient irrigation systems, all of which bolster resilience to climate change while empowering women as catalysts for positive transformation.

Finally, the study suggests that, given the fluctuating precipitation and rising temperatures, Foya District farming methods might need to change with more drought-resistant crops and better irrigation methods should be put into perspective. There should be proper information points about the need for improved water management plans to deal with the possibility of floods in years of heavy rainfall and water scarcity in years of less precipitation. Adaptation will be critical for establishing better societies now and in the future. We must adjust every aspect of our society, from how we obtain food and water, to keeping everyone well and providing safe shelter. It is also suggested that additional research be done on this topic to provide different methods to help enhance the transition to carbon-neutral agriculture.

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Conflict of Interests

No conflict of interest.

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